

AN ANALYSIS OF TEACHERS’ PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

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Abstract: This research aims to analyze the teachers’ pedagogical competence which concerns more on how the teachers able to manage the classroom and use the instructional media in teaching English for young learners. Being a teacher is not as easy as the people think, because “the teachers play an important role in what they do, and how they do in developing their own professional knowledge and practice” (Loughran, 2006, as cited in Livia, 2010: 1). They also need to have teaching skills or pedagogical competence (Hotaman, 2010). Therefore, this research focuses on the teachers’ pedagogical competence which consists of classroom management and the use of instructional media

Key words: EYL classroom, pedagogical competence, classroom management, instructional media

Competence can be defined as knowledge, skills and abilities that are controlled by someone who has been a part of himself so that he can perform 8 cognitive, effective and psychomotor behaviors as well as possible. According to Usman (1994), the competence is “the one thing that describes a person’s qualifications or ability both qualitatively and quantitatively”. This notion implies that the competence can be used in two contexts, namely: firstly, as an indicator of ability that shows the acts observed; secondly, as a concept that includes aspects of cognitive, effective and acts as well as the stages of implementation as a whole. In the other hand, competence is an underlying characteristic of an individual that is causally related to criterion-referenced effective and/or superior performance in a job or situation.

Underlying characteristics means the competency is a fairly deep and enduring part of a person's personality and can predict behavior in a wide variety of situations and tasks. Causally related means that a competency causes or predict behavior and performance. Criterion referenced means that the competency actually predicts who does something well or poorly, as measured on a specific criterion or standard (Spencer and Spencer, 1993:9). From discussion above, it can be conclude that the competence refers to the ability to implement something that is acquired through education. Competence refers to the performance of teachers and act rationally to meet certain specifications in carrying out educational tasks. It is said to be rational because competence has direction and purpose, while performance is the behavior of a real person who is observed by others. According to Gordon, as quoted by E. Mulyasa (2007: 38), that there are six aspects or domains contained in the concept of competence, namely as follows: 1) Knowledge, is an awareness in cognitive field, for example a teacher knows how to identify learning needs, and how to perform the learning of the students according to their needs. 2) Comprehension (understanding), is the depth of cognitive and affective owned by individuals, for example, a teacher who would carry out the study must have a good understanding of the characteristics and circumstances of learners. 9 3) Ability (skill), is something that is owned by an individual to perform a task or job assigned to him, such as the ability of teachers to choose and create simple props to provide ease of learning to learners. 4) Values, is a standard of behavior that has been believed and psychologically been fused in a person, for example, the standard behavior of teachers in learning (honesty, openness, democratic, and others). 5) Attitude, is feeling (happy, unhappy, likes, dislikes) or a reaction to a stimulus that comes from outside, a reaction to the economic crisis, the feeling of 11 Февраль 2021 10-қисм Тошкент the salary increase, and others. 6) Interest, is the tendency of a person to perform an act, such as interests to do something or to learn something. From the six aspects contained in the concept of the competence above, if it explored deeply include four areas of competence that is essential for a teacher namely pedagogical competence, personal competence, social

competence, and professional competence. These four types of these competencies should be controlled fully by the teacher.

Awareness of the competencies demanded a heavy responsibility for the teachers themselves. They must have the courage to face the challenges of the task and the environment, which would affect the development of his personality. It means they also must have the courage to change and improve themselves in accordance with the demands of the times. Competence is the ability of a person to exercise or perform a job or task that is based on skills, knowledge and attitudes supported by work in accordance with the demands of the job. Pedagogical Competence is one type of competencies that absolutely need to be mastered by teachers. Basically, pedagogical competence is the ability of teachers to manage the education of students. Pedagogical competence refers to skills of teachers to deal with three aspects of teaching skills, namely lesson planning, implementing teaching and learning process, and assessing students’ learning. According to Susilo (2011: 115), pedagogical competence is the ability of teachers to manage the education of students, include: setting up the learning device, implementing the learning, and evaluation. In this study, the researcher only focus on one aspect of pedagogical competences namely the ability of teachers to implement the learning process that consists of how the teachers manage classroom and use instructional media

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